

Coding Summary by File Beyond Open Research II 22/08/2025 08:48

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Dataset

Files\\Research data lifecycle balloons and rocks exercise

Code

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data

Yes	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
0.2687	17	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Promote a culture of data sharing					
		2	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Resource / data management champion (to relieve the pressure + lack of clarity)					
		3	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
No follow up, lack of peer reviews of data management plan					
		4	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Procedures for personelle exit - handover data + protocols.					
		5	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Filenaming convention agreed to + followed by all data collectors + processors.					
		6	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
No conventios for file naming that can make finding data later very difficult.					
		7	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Data processing and analysis not trialled during acquisition so 'quality data' not always collectd without that feedback					
		8	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Within the institute, collective effort to process/analyse data workshop/bioinformation facility to help					

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
share (data processing and analysis)				9	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Open data platforms				10	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Better data management plans				11	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Cost of data maintenance				12	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Paying people to know when to share data, when is for patients etc and paying for patients data copyrights				13	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse				14	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Having data stewards				15	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Keeping data annotated				16	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Sharing data with ID's that are universally recognised; sharing data with the latest updated correctly annotated				17	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data management						
	Yes	0.0689	4			
Resource / data management champion (to relieve the pressure + lack of clarity)				1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
No follow up, lack of peer reviews of data management plan				2	NV	18/08/2025 10:23

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Permanent lab manager				3	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Better data management plans				4	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data management\data management champion						
	No	0.0172	1			
Resource / data management champion (to relieve the pressure + lack of clarity)				1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data management\data management plan						
	No	0.0344	2			
No follow up, lack of peer reviews of data management plan				1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Better data management plans				2	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data management\permanent lab manager						
	No	0.0172	1			
Permanent lab manager				1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\analyse data workshop						
	No	0.0172	1			
Within the institute, collective effort to process/analyse data workshop/bioinformation facility to help				1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\data collectors

No	0.0144	1
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1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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Filenaming convention agreed to + followed by all data collectors + processors.

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\data maintenance

No	0.0172	1
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1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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Cost of data maintenance

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\data management champion

No	0.0172	1
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1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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Resource / data management champion (to relieve the pressure + lack of clarity)

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\data management plan

No	0.0344	2
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1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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No follow up, lack of peer reviews of data management plan

2	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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Better data management plans

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\data platforms

No	0.0172	1
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1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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Open data platforms

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\data processing

No	0.0071	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
share (data processing and analysis)						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\data stewards

No	0.0172	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Having data stewards						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\finding data

No	0.0082	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
No conventios for file naming that can make finding data later very difficult.						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\handover data

No	0.0147	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Procedures for personelle exit - handover data + protocols.						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\keeping data

No	0.0172	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23	
Keeping data annotated						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
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Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\patients data copyrights

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0172	1		1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23

Paying people to know when to share data, when is for patients etc and paying for patients data copyrights

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\quality data

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0344	2		1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23

Data processing and analysis not trialled during acquisition so 'quality data' not always collected without that feedback

				2	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\data\sharing data

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
No	0.0344	2		1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23

Promote a culture of data sharing

				2	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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Sharing data with ID's that are universally recognised; sharing data with the latest updated correctly annotated

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\people

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Yes	0.0517	4		1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23

If your study involves vulnerable people there are a lot of different requirements for consent + forms to fill in

				2	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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Paying people to know when to share data, when is for patients etc and paying for patients data copyrights

				3	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
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People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse						

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\people\\paying people

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0172	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
Paying people to know when to share data, when is for patients etc and paying for patients data copyrights					

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\people\\people power

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0172	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse					

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\people\\people time

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0172	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse					

Codes\\Autocoded Themes\\people\\vulnerable people

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0172	1	1	NV	18/08/2025 10:23
If your study involves vulnerable people there are a lot of different requirements for consent + forms to fill in					

Codes\\Collaboration & communication

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.0517	3	1	JS	18/08/2025 10:28
Promote a culture of data sharing					

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	18/08/2025 12:12
People sometimes want to keep their data to themselves. Sharing isn't in their interests						
				3	JS	18/08/2025 15:19
Lack of communication between IT departments and working researchers to understand their real needs and potential solutions						
Codes\\Data Management						
	No	0.2758	16			
				1	JS	18/08/2025 12:10
Resource / data management champion (to relieve the pressure + lack of clarity)						
				2	JS	18/08/2025 12:10
No follow up, lack of peer reviews of data management plan						
				3	JS	18/08/2025 12:12
People sometimes want to keep their data to themselves. Sharing isn't in their interests						
				4	JS	18/08/2025 12:13
Different disciplines have different needs/approaches						
				5	JS	19/08/2025 08:11
Permanent lab manager						
				6	JS	18/08/2025 15:20
No conventios for file naming that can make finding data later very difficult. Need for a formalised convention. Need for good practice to be embeded from beginning						
				7	JS	18/08/2025 15:21
Loss of data when colleagues move on to a different post/organisation						
				8	JS	19/08/2025 08:05
Lack of accessibility to data: accessing each other data						
				9	JS	19/08/2025 08:07
Compromising the amount of data you can export due to space e.g. not exporting negative results						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				10	JS	19/08/2025 08:07
Due to the size of datasets complications to duplicate/backup those datasets						
				11	JS	19/08/2025 08:08
Data stewards - faculty embedded, disciplinary /domain-specific RDM support						
				12	JS	19/08/2025 08:16
Better data management plans						
				13	JS	19/08/2025 08:17
Can't find it						
				14	JS	19/08/2025 08:23
People power - pay for people time to analyse and improve data quality for future discoverability and reuse						
				15	JS	19/08/2025 08:23
Having data stewards						
				16	JS	19/08/2025 08:25
Sharing data with ID's that are universal recognised; sharing data with the latest updated correctly annotated						
Codes\\Infrastructure & resources						
	No	0.2068	12			
				1	JS	18/08/2025 10:28
Setting up infrastructure to support + educate staff + students						
				2	JS	18/08/2025 12:12
Lack of time (time pressure)						
				3	JS	18/08/2025 12:13
Part of appraisal?						
				4	JS	18/08/2025 12:13
Shared folder policy						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				5	JS	18/08/2025 12:14
Unlimited storage. Server + tape						
				6	JS	19/08/2025 08:06
Old IT equipment that means some files can only be accessed via specific PC. If that PC dies some data is not accessible anymore						
				7	JS	19/08/2025 08:06
Data storage: limitation in the capacity						
				8	JS	19/08/2025 08:12
Within the institute, collective effort to process/analyse data workshop/bioinformation facility to help						
				9	JS	19/08/2025 08:13
Open data platforms						
				10	JS	19/08/2025 08:22
Cost of data maintenance						
				11	JS	19/08/2025 08:23
Paying people to know when to share data, when is for patients etc and paying for patients data copyrights						
				12	JS	19/08/2025 08:24
Software and hardware obsolescence						
Codes\\Policy & governance						
	No	0.1896	11			
				1	JS	18/08/2025 12:05
More follow up + support from funders						
				2	JS	18/08/2025 12:06
Set up a standard directory structure for everyone to follow/use from the start						
				3	JS	18/08/2025 12:08
If the funder doesn't ask for something specifically, you might not think about doing it						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				4	JS	18/08/2025 12:12
If your study involves vulnerable people there are a lot of different requirements for consent + forms to fill in						
				5	JS	18/08/2025 12:13
Procedures for personelle exit - handover data + protocols. Checklist						
				6	JS	18/08/2025 12:13
Filenaming convention agreed to + followed by all data collectors + processors. Samples + data						
				7	JS	18/08/2025 12:13
Shared folder policy						
				8	JS	18/08/2025 12:14
Regular review of policies + procedures. Do they need changing?						
				9	JS	19/08/2025 08:13
Consequences for not archiving						
				10	JS	19/08/2025 08:16
Standardised RDM policty for all Imperial						
				11	JS	19/08/2025 08:22
Not wanting to share						

Codes\\Research data lifecycle ballons and rocks exercise\\Transcription

No	1.0000	58
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1	JS	18/08/2025 10:23
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Codes\\Training & education

No	0.1896	11
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1	JS	18/08/2025 10:29
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Setting up infrastrcuture to support + educate staff + students

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	18/08/2025 10:29
Training and education to gain experiences						
				3	JS	18/08/2025 12:08
Lack of knowledge/understanding/experience (eg students)						
				4	JS	19/08/2025 08:12
Paper based record keeping culture to physicaly[?] share (data processing and analysis)						
				5	JS	19/08/2025 08:13
Amount of data Large datasets - still trying to figure out how to analyse/process it don't feel is ready/accurate to share						
				6	JS	19/08/2025 08:13
[?] that methogology is not yet robust - lack confidence [?] shares in case [?]						
				7	JS	19/08/2025 08:14
Education						
				8	JS	19/08/2025 08:21
Data archiving and sharing: Resources "umbrella term" consistency						
				9	JS	19/08/2025 08:24
Balance metadata requirements in a reasonable amount of time that other people will read it						
				10	JS	19/08/2025 08:24
Keeping data annotated						
				11	JS	19/08/2025 08:24
Machine vs Human discoverabilty and reuse						
Codes\\Trustworthiness						
	No	0.1551	9			
				1	JS	19/08/2025 08:06
Lack of accessibility to data: accessing each other data						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				2	JS	19/08/2025 08:06
Data processing and analysis not trialled during acquisition so 'quality data' not always collected without that feedback						
				3	JS	19/08/2025 08:07
Quality assurance/peer review for all data: a new post[?] is allocated to each research project						
				4	JS	19/08/2025 08:16
Data archiving and sharing; more transparency; policies more findable						
				5	JS	19/08/2025 08:16
Make PI's accountable for RDM + DM [?]						
				6	JS	19/08/2025 08:16
Transparency of policies						
				7	JS	19/08/2025 08:17
Password protected						
				8	JS	19/08/2025 08:22
Interpretability e.g. code interpretation clear where data came from						
				9	JS	19/08/2025 08:22
Corrupted data						